

Studies of the Conductances and Energetics of Transport of Sodium Acetate, Benzoate and Salicylate in an uncharged Microporous Membrane

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Studies on the conductance behaviour of an 'uncharged' microporous membrane bathed in sodium salt solutions of organic anions, viz. acetate (Ac^-), salicylate (SI^-) and benzoate (Bz^-) at different concentrations (1–200 mol m^{-3}) and in the temperature range 298–323 K are reported. The values show a smooth increase in conductance at all concentrations, tending towards limiting values, and maintain the order, $\text{SI}^- > \text{Bz}^- > \text{Ac}^-$ reverse to that in aqueous solution over the temperature range studied here. This reversal of order has been correlated with the kind of ion-pairing termed as 'localised hydrolysis' supposed to be more predominant within the micropores. The $\text{p}K_a$ values and hence the proton binding affinity of the conjugate bases showing the order, $\text{Ac}^- > \text{Bz}^- > \text{SI}^-$ may justify the conductance in the reverse order. The temperature variation of conductance has been utilised to calculate the activation energies assuming the applicability of Arrhenius equation. The energy values follow the order $E_{\text{Ac}^-} > E_{\text{SI}^-} > E_{\text{Bz}^-}$. The highest energy for the acetate ion is in conformity with its lowest conductance, but the higher activation energy value for SI^- than that of Bz^- may well be explained in the light of extra energy required for endothermic opening up of intramolecular hydrogen bonding of SI^- before undergoing localised hydrolysis during the conductance.

Studies on the transport phenomena through various types of membranes are necessary to interpret mechanism of transport of biological membranes *in vivo*, and also to understand the potential use of the membranes in industrial separation processes. Extensive work has been done with different artificial membranes charged or weakly charged^{1–3}, but sufficient data are not available for 'uncharged' porous membranes since these are not easily available in suitable forms for the studies of transport phenomena. Recently Samanta and Basu have shown that the microporous membranes of Mizutani^{4,5} prepared from the ion-exchange membranes of 'Neosepta' family⁶ and the millipore filter papers⁷ may be suitably utilised as 'uncharged' membranes for the studies on the conductance behaviour and energetics of transport of alkali chlorides^{7,8}, and of halides, halates and nitrate of potassium⁹.

The present studies record some interesting observations of conductances and energetics of transport of biologically important anions, acetate (Ac^-), benzoate (Bz^-) and salicylate (SI^-) through the 'uncharged' microporous membrane⁵.

Results and Discussion

The membrane thickness and the average pore radius are 0.15 mm and 26 nm respectively, and the tortuosity factor⁵ is between 1.5 and 2.0.

The conductance (C) and hence the specific conductance (κ) were determined in the concentration range 1–200 mol m^{-3} at suitable intervals in the temperature range 298–323 K with the interval of 5 degree. Fig. 1(A) reflects the variations of the κ values of these anions with concentration at a particular temperature (298 K). General trend found for all these electrolytes is that the values increase smoothly from a low value at extreme dilution tending towards limiting values after certain high concentrations. This characteristic behaviour of the limiting tendency of membrane conductance at higher concentrations was also observed by some earlier workers^{2,10,11} with their different types of charged membranes. The plausible explanation for the limiting tendency in this 'uncharged' microporous membrane may be given in the light of competition between two factors : with increase in bathing con-

Fig. 1. (A) Plots of specific conductance (κ) of (Δ) acetate, ($\square$) benzoate and ($\circ$) salicylate of sodium through microporous membrane against bathing concentrations at 298 K. (B) Plots of specific conductance (κ) of (Δ) sodium acetate against bathing concentrations at different temperatures (298–323 K), the lowest one is at 298 with increase by 5 degree interval in the upward direction having the highest one at 323 K.

centration the pore should be occupied by greater amount of salt with tendency to increase conductance but because of expulsion of water from the pores due to osmotic effect as the external bathing concentration increases the ionic mobility will be decreased lowering the conductance. After a certain concentration the two factors may more or less balance each other tending towards the limiting values. The conjecture of large water content within the pores in the dilute range, and the expulsion of water at higher concentration in case of 'uncharged' microporous membrane was verified experimentally earlier by Samanta and Basu⁷.

The same test performed with this microporous membrane in presence of the organic anion salts also substantiates the idea of exclusion of water at higher bathing concentrations. The specific weights (W_s), of the wet membrane (W_s) calculated by the formula, $W_s = (W_s - W_d)/W_d$, where W_d is the weight of the dry membrane, show the initial increase and then decrease with the increase in the bathing concentrations.

The κ values in the micropores follow the order, $\text{SI}^- > \text{Bz}^- > \text{Ac}^-$ showing the different sequence of conductances in aqueous bulk solution¹², where it is $\text{Ac}^- > \text{SI}^- > \text{Bz}^-$. The change in this order indicates that the ionic movement and hence the conductance

within the micropores are affected by some other factors which though exist in aqueous bulk solution become more prominent within the pores. One of the plausible explanations may be put forward in the light of the kind of ion-pairing with H^+ and OH^- of water acting as intermediary with the pattern, $\text{M}^+ \dots \text{OH}^- \dots \text{H}^+ \dots \text{A}^-$ termed as 'localised hydrolysis' by Robinson *et al.*^{12,13} which may be more predominant in the micropores. The degree of this type of ion-pairing depends on the proton affinity of the conjugate base, A^- . The $\text{p}K_a$ values of these organic acids at 298 K follow the order¹², Ac^- (4.8) $>$ Bz^- (4.2) $>$ SI^- (3.0), and hence the proton bindings due to 'localised hydrolysis' should follow the same order. The preference for ion-pairing due to this 'hydrolysis' being the least in salicylate ion and the most in acetate ion, the conductances follow the order from salicylate to acetate.

As regards the temperature effect, the change in the membrane conductance (κ) is shown in Fig. 1(B) with a particular salt, sodium acetate. The general trend at any temperature is the same showing an almost smooth increase with concentration tending towards a limiting value. The value at any particular concentration increases with increasing temperature. Almost the same behaviour has been found for the other two organic anions studied here. The temperature variation of conductances of the sodium salts of these anions also maintains the same order. Since the swelling effect in this 'uncharged' microporous membrane is negligible, the increase in conductance at any elevated temperature may be attributed mainly because of increase in mobility rather than greater salt uptake due to swelling as are presumed in 'charged' membrane^{2,10,11}.

Arrhenius equation in its basic form¹⁴ has been applied replacing the reaction rate constant by the specific conductance (κ) and $\log \kappa$ values are plotted against $1/T$ at each concentration to calculate the Arrhenius activation energies (E_A) of conduction from the slopes. Fig. 2 shows plots at a concentration of 50 mol m^{-3} , where the smooth lines suggest that there is no abrupt irreversible change in the membrane structure within the temperature range studied. The con-

Fig. 2. Plots of $\log \kappa$ values of the organic sodium salts at a particular concentration (50 mol m^{-3}) against $1/T$ for the calculation of Arrhenius activation energies from the slope, $E/2.303 R$.

centration dependence of the activation energy (Fig. 3) follows the same characteristic pattern as observed earlier in 'uncharged' membranes with other electrolytes⁷⁻⁹. The energy values, very high at low concentration, fall sharply with the next concentration, and gradually decrease with further increase in concentration. The high activation energy values at extremely low concentration indicate some kind of immobilisation of the ions within the pores, possibly due to adsorption on the pore walls because of the presence of any residual charge undetected by the usual chemical methods and this has been overcome with the increase in concentration.

Study of the energetics of transport of these organic anions through this 'uncharged' microporous membrane reveals some further interesting aspects. The activation energy values do not exactly follow the reverse order of conductance like the case of alkali chlorides^{7,8}, where the hydrated sizes of the cations play the important role, but has some characteristics common with the energy of activations of halides⁹. The perusal of Fig. 3 shows that the average order over the concentration range is $E_{Ac} > E_{Sl} > E_{Bz}$. The highest activation energy value E_{Ac} conforms to the lowest

Fig. 3. Plots of activation energies of the different organic sodium salts calculated from Fig. 2 against the respective bathing concentration of the electrolytes on an arbitrary concentration axis mentioning the values at the respective concentration only.

conductance of the acetate ion suggesting also the mechanism of obstruction because of relatively high degree of 'localised hydrolysis'. However, the order of E_{Sl} and E_{Bz} is not in accordance with the conductance pattern. It needs clarification as to the Sl^- having the higher conductance also needs higher activation energy than that of Bz^- . The simple idea of 'activation theory' regarding the ionic movement is that the ion occupies an average equilibrium configuration surrounded by solvent molecules, and that it is continuously 'jumping' from one equilibrium position to another, and the average energy required for this 'movement' or jumping is the activation energy¹⁵. If some secondary phenomena take place these may require some extra energy along with the normal activation energy for jumping. It is well known that salicylic acid because of its intramolecular hydrogen bonding has many physical properties different from those of similar acids¹⁶. In this context it may be presumed that this intramolecular hydrogen bonding in salicylic acid is playing an important role, where the endothermic opening up of this hydrogen bond before the involvement of Sl^- in the 'localised hydrolysis' within the membrane phase needs an extra energy in addition to the activation energy requires for conductance making $E_{Sl^-} > E_{Bz^-}$.

Experimental

The microporous membrane was prepared following the reported method⁵ by treatment of a 'Neosepta' anion-exchange membrane in $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{-3}$ form with 5–6% aqueous solution of H_2O_2 at 298 K with intermittent stirring for about 10 days. The porous membrane showing microporosity with complete loss of ion-exchange capacity was finally washed with deionised water to remove absorbed chemicals. The setting up the conductance cell and bathing of the membranes with the respective electrolytes at different concentrations at various temperatures was followed as reported earlier^{7–9}. The conductance (C) measurement was carried out with a Systronic 303 instrument at 1 kHz using the technique originally developed by Subrahmanyam and Lakshminarayanaiah¹⁷ and recently followed by various workers^{2,3,7–9}. The cell was placed in a thermostat maintained at the desired temperature (± 0.1). The specific conductance was calculated by the usual formula, $\kappa = (l/a) C$, where l is the distance between the two mercury surfaces, i.e. the thickness of the membrane and a the effective area of the membrane surfaces, i.e. the area of opening of the flanged ends of the U-tube which keeps the membrane sandwiched between the two mercury surfaces. Solutions were prepared with A.R. grade sodium salts of acetate, benzoate and silylate.

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